

OpenAIRE
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National Open Access Report for Ireland

Visualisation samples

Goals

- Present a series of visual presentations to finalize selections for Monitor dashboards and the Report.
- The focus centers on types/colours of Open Access (OA) and the aspects of unrealized OA.
- The numbers you observe are a sample and not final.

Option 1

- This is the current selection in the report. Green OA encompasses publications irrespective of their licensing status, and Unrealized Open Access includes bronze and closed publications.

Repository mediated (green) vs publisher mediated OA (gold, hybrid)
over time

Unrealized Open Access
over time

Option 2

- In this option, Green OA is divided into two subcategories: those with a license and those without. Publications in Green OA without a license are reclassified under "Unrealized Open Access." They appear in a separate column, combined with Bronze publications, as both types are accessible (as opposed to closed) under the unrealized category.

Repository mediated (green with license) vs publisher mediated OA (gold, hybrid)
over time

Unrealised Open Access
over time

Option 3

- In the third option, Green OA is again based on the presence or absence of a license. Furthermore, the distinction between repository-mediated and publisher-mediated Open Access is expanded into three categories: repository OA only, publisher OA only, and a combination of both. This allows for stacking these three series as their numbers do not overlap. Additionally, Gold and Hybrid Open Access are combined under Publisher OA. To adequately represent this, an additional graph would be necessary to illustrate the split between Gold and Hybrid Open Access.

Repository OA vs Publisher OA
over time

Unrealised Open Access
over time

Option 4

- Similar to option 3, but presented in percentage terms. This allows for a direct comparison of the different categories in relative terms.

Repository OA vs Publisher OA
over time

Unrealised Open Access
over time

Option 5

Our recommended approach, comprising three distinct graphs, offers a comprehensive view of Open Access (OA) trends. The first graph, by juxtaposing Green OA with a license against Gold and Hybrid, effectively tracks the evolution of repository versus publisher-mediated OA over time. The second graph, presenting data as percentages, facilitates an understanding of preferences between repository-only, publisher-only, and dual-mediated OA, highlighting shifts in OA practices. Finally, the third graph's separation of unrealized OA into accessible and closed categories provides clarity on the accessibility landscape.

Thank you!